

Transition towards environment friendly consumer products by co-creation of an oxidoreductase foundry

GA No 101000607

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st June 2021. End date: 31st May 2025

D1.1: Stakeholder mapping and methodology for stakeholder engagement v1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000607

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Deliverable log

Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable title	Stakeholder mapping and methodology for stakeholder engagement
Description of deliverable	<i>D1.1. Stakeholder mapping and methodology for stakeholder engagement. Landscape analysis to identify stakeholders in four key groups (Research, Business, Policy and Society).</i>
Deliverable type – X on relevant	<input type="checkbox"/> Website, patents filing, etc. <input type="checkbox"/> ORDP Open Research Data Pilot <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Report <input type="checkbox"/> Demonstrator <input type="checkbox"/> Ethics <input type="checkbox"/> Other
WP number	WP1
Deliverable due date	30-11-2021
Submission date	30-11-2021
Dissemination levels – X on relevant	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Public <input type="checkbox"/> Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
Lead beneficiary- organisation	<i>SBSM</i>
Responsible person	<i>Susanne Hollmann</i>
Name and affiliation contributing persons	<i>Babette Regierer (SBSM)</i>
Name and affiliation internal reviewers	<i>Gro Bjerga (NORCE)</i> Christina Rørvik. (NORCE) Lesley Tobin (REDINN)

Document history and changes

Version	Date	Author	Description
V1.0	30-11-2021	SH	Final version uploaded

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Summary

The vision of OXIPRO is to contribute to the transition towards greener sunscreens, home textiles, nutraceuticals, and detergents, and to the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. This will be done by building an open and collaborative cross-border, cross-sectoral innovation ecosystem that fosters the development of novel enzymes - and specifically oxidoreductases - for environment-friendly consumer products. To achieve this goal, interaction with and engagement of stakeholders becomes crucial.

OXIPRO's sees its stakeholders as those individual(s), group(s), or organisation(s) who may affect, be affected by, or perceive itself to be affected by its activities or outcomes. Four thematic areas were identified from which these stakeholders originate: **Research, Industry, Society and Policy (STAKEHOLDER AREAS)**. To maximise OXIPRO's impact requires a clear understanding of the interests and influence of the stakeholders and a strategy to address their needs. D1.1 details procedures and criteria which will be used to identify and recruit individuals and/ or groups for information exchange, and how they will be engaged.

The aim of this deliverable is to enable OXIPRO to optimally inform, exchange, engage with and include stakeholders or groups that positively influence OXIPRO, and to reduce the risk that a stakeholder or group will negatively impact the project. This requires management of both, those with a negative view of the changes who need to be carefully reflected on and considered for potential damage minimisation, and those with a positive view whose influence needs to be maximised.

D1.1 is a stand-alone document, which explains OXIPRO's approach to stakeholder mapping and their engagement. The underlying stakeholder register will be continuously revised. New contacts will be added as a result of OXIPRO's communication and engagement activities. The stakeholder register (as of November 30th, 2021) will not become part of D1.1 for GDPR reasons-

List of abbreviations and definitions

1. Abbreviations

R&I	Research and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
AREA	Anticipate, reflect, engage, and act
KSA	Key Stakeholder Area
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
NGO's	Non-Governmental Organisations
ISO	International Standardisation Organisation
CDP	Communication and dissemination Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network EEN
CLIB	Cluster for Industrial Biotechnology (Germany)
EEA	European Economic Area
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
FNR	Food and Natural Resources
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
M	Milestone
T	Task

2. Definitions:

STAKEHOLDER	Individuals, groups or organisations who are directly or indirectly affected by OXIPRO's activities or who have an interest in OXIPROs activities and /or outcomes or who are relevant for the projects progress and success
STAKEHOLDER REGISTER	List of stakeholders
KEY STAKEHOLDER AREA	Research, politics, economy, and society as a superordinate area to which the stakeholders will be allocated
STAKEHOLDER GROUPS	individuals, groups or organisations from stakeholder sectors who have a legitimate interest in the course or outcome of OXIPRO
STAKEHOLDER SECTOR	OXIPRO addresses different products sectors (cosmetics, home textiles, from which the stakeholder will be selected. The different Stakeholder Sectors are represented in each key stakeholder area.
STAKEHOLDER MAP	The categorised stakeholder register while considering stakeholder sectors and groups depending on their influence / interest priority groups

1 Introduction - Purpose

The purpose of stakeholder mapping is to describe OXIPRO's stakeholder network and develop an overall approach to stakeholder engagement. The analysis will identify who exactly we should engage, inform and/or encourage to participate during the project's phase – and to what extent.

Therefore, in WP1 T1.1, we first identify the most relevant target audiences and carry out the initial mapping among them. In parallel, we collect the first contacts whom the consortium reaches out to either via partners existing contacts or OXIPRO's communication and engagement activities. In addition, we explore the needs of the identified groups and provides a basis for the project's value proposition, which will be further extended in the project's dissemination strategy.

Not all stakeholders are made equal. Nor do they all deserve the same amount of attention. The stakeholder analysis enables us to properly identify all stakeholders and to categorise them in order of importance as it pertains to our efforts to secure social acceptance and ensure successful project delivery. We will uncover any potential risks, issues or misunderstanding that could disrupt the project. This information is vital for knowing what type of communication and messaging will best help to minimise perceived negative impacts and amplify positive impacts. Thus, the resulting information will strongly influence our stakeholder management strategy and messaging. The stakeholder analysis will be ongoing to monitor if and how our stakeholder groups are changing over time – in terms of who they are, how their needs or expectations may be evolving, and how your relationship with them has improved – or deteriorated. Stakeholders may have various degrees of interest and influence on the project activities and results. This is considered as part of OXIPRO's stakeholder mapping methodology. The initial network of stakeholders, attached to this report, concentrates on those stakeholders that were carefully assessed using the identification and mapping methodology described in this report. New contacts will be made, and connections will be built during the project's runtime, and it is expected that our list of stakeholders (**STAKEHOLDER REGISTER**) and thus engagement will evolve over time. The stakeholder register and its resulting categorisation into priority groups (**STAKEHOLDER MAP**) will be periodically reviewed, revised, and adjusted. The same applies for the resulting activities for the stakeholder's engagement.

The report includes the following parts:

1. Description of objectives and scope of the stakeholder mapping.
 - Relation to other deliverables.
2. Description of the methodology.
 - Stakeholder definition
 - Analyse stakeholders by impact and influence

- Presentation of the mapping process and its preliminary results Inc. draft of the stakeholders' needs and value proposition for each stakeholder group.
 - Stakeholder communication and reporting strategy
 - Engagement with stakeholders
- 3 List of stakeholder's' needs for each stakeholder group.
4. Attachment

2 Objectives and scope

D1.1 (Stakeholder mapping and methodology for stakeholder engagement) is a living document, which explains OXIPRO's approach to stakeholder mapping and engagement and provides an initial stakeholder map. The stakeholder register will be continuously revised and updated with new contacts added as a result of OXIPROs communication, dissemination, and engagement activities. as well as cluster missions, open calls, etc. It will be continuously monitored if and how our stakeholder groups are changing over time – in terms of who they are, how their needs or expectations may be evolving, and how our relationship with them has improved – or deteriorated. Hence D1.1 will be a living document which will be continuously revised and adjusted and become extended according to the new contacts added. The final updated stakeholder register (confidential not public) and its resulting stakeholder map will be finalised by the end of the project.

The objectives and scope of stakeholder mapping align with the seven objectives of OXIPRO:

1. To speed-up systemic innovation and boost market uptake
2. To accelerate and rationalise the selection and design of oxidoreductases
3. To fast-track screening and optimisation of oxidoreductases
4. To establish an efficient oxidoreductase production
5. To boost innovation
6. To assess the sustainability, circularity, and safety of developed consumer products
7. To ensure communication and dissemination of OXIPRO results and benefits

The stakeholders form the priority audience for the communication and dissemination plan (CDP), and outcomes of stakeholder engagement will be used to refine the content of OXIPROs communication and dissemination plan (WP7).

In D1.1 we will identify different stakeholders, categorise them into different priority groups and start building the community which should ensure greater acceptance and wider applicability of the project results. To meet this, the objectives of D1.1 are as following:

- to define the stakeholder mapping methodology;
- to identify the first list of relevant stakeholders which will be enriched during the project lifetime;

- to categorise them in order of importance as it pertains to our efforts and to secure social acceptance;
- to define needs and key value propositions for all stakeholder categories which will be used for further communication and engagement activities.

2.1 Relation to other WP, deliverables, and tasks

D1.1 influences and forms the basis of workflows in several WPs which are listed in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 List of WPs, Tasks and Deliverables which are depending on or influenced by D1.1

WP	Task	Deliverable
2	T.2.4. In silico bioprospecting modules	
4	T.4.1 Host selection, cloning and small-scale production	
4	T.4.3. Process simulation/modelling and large-scale enzyme production	
5	T.5.5. Novel Opportunities	
6	T.6.1. Environmental sustainability including Carbon footprint and Carbon handprint	D6.2
6	T.6.2. Social and economic sustainability	
6	T.6.3. Circularity of value-chains	
7	T.7.1. Communication and Dissemination plan, social media, and project website	D7.1, D7.2, D7.3, D7.4
7	T.7.2. Corporate identity, content management and communication/dissemination material	
7	T.7.3. Networking, events, and publications	
7	T.7.4. Social awareness on consumer products of the future	
8	T.8.4. Data Management Plan	D8.2

3 Methodology

It is crucial to ensure that we engage with the correct stakeholders from the beginning of OXIPRO to avoid spending time and effort on audiences that are less or not relevant for the project. It is important to ensure that the Stakeholder List includes those stakeholders that have a high potential to engage and participate in OXIPROs activities. For these reasons, we run a Landscape analysis for Stakeholder management, using Stakeholder Analysis matrix and the Power-Interest matrix developed by A.L. Mendelow [1] to analysing the power/interest stakeholders have over OXIPRO, with a

target of >100 stakeholders engaged at European level. The stakeholder mapping process comprises three phases which are built on each other, and it will end with a final fourth phase of engagement (Figure 1). The stakeholders form the priority audience for the communication and dissemination plan, and outcomes of stakeholder engagement will be used to refine the content (WP7). The process is not static as we will extend and adjust the mapping throughout the runtime of OXIPRO.

3.1 Phase 1: Collection of stakeholders

OXIPRO has different impacts on and different value expectations for the stakeholders potentially engaged with the project. In the first phase we identify and collect all potential stakeholders without any verification or screening. All are represented in the stakeholder register, which enables stakeholders to be filtered and facilitates the identification of those required for targeted activities. Identified stakeholders at this stage include everyone who might potentially have some interest in OXIPROs activities and results. During this phase, all project partners are involved, building upon their own contact networks. For this, all partners receive an excel sheet (Annex 1) which needs to be filled in. After they have signed the DTA developed as outlined in the Ethics deliverables the sheets will be sent to SBSM for phase 2: analysis, categorisation, and prioritisation of stakeholders. Collection of

stakeholders does start via online search from month 3 and the contribution by partners after they have signed the Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) from month 6.

Currently, OXIPRO has identified four major Key Stakeholder Areas from which stakeholders will be targeted. The four key stakeholder areas (KSA) are **Research, Industry, Policy, and Society**. These KSA's are further divided in four stakeholder sectors mirroring the four targeted for environment-friendly consumer product new products **Sun Care, Home Textiles, Detergents and Nutraceuticals**. Each KSA consist of multiple **stakeholder groups** applied to the four stakeholder sectors (Figure 2).

KEY STAKEHOLDER AREAS

Figure 2: Key Stakeholder Areas, Sectors and Groups from which identified individuals, groups or organisations will enter the stakeholder register and the stakeholder map.

3.2 Phase 2: Categorisation into groups

In the second phase an analysis is carried out to identify the stakeholders' relevance to, interest in, and perception of OXIPRO. This ongoing analysis has been performed by undertaking desktop research focussing on and evaluating stakeholders' recent activities, as well as their interest in OXIPRO's innovative technologies and future products. Because of the delay caused by the need to implement WP9 and its deliverables at the stage of the expected delivery of D1.1, the analysis has been done by a desk search. For the analysis, we first separate the individuals into two main audiences: internal and external individuals/stakeholders, as outlined in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Criteria for differentiation between internal and external stakeholders and resulting communication route

Who?	Reason to involve with OXIPRO, interest and benefits	Route	WP
OXIPRO's executives, their administrations, Boards, EC	Management of OXIPRO (coordinating team, the scientific committee, the management committee, and the SAB) and the EC. All wish the see the project succeed. They have additional communication requirements and need to be made aware of project status so that they can decide what, if any, issues need to be escalated to the next executive level. Shareholders.	Internal	WP7 T7.1 WP8 T8.1, T8.5
The project members	Other projects such as e.g., the H2020 FNR-16 sister projects, local committees, and institutional boards such as e.g., faculty, institute, or work councils, labor unions. Some boards have a desire to maintain the standards in a certain area. Their power to stop the project can range from zero to full Identification of committees and boards that impact our activities. OXIPRO must consider their interest.	Internal	WP7 T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4 WP8 T8.1, T8.5
Individuals, customers, end users, government, regulatory bodies, public who have a stake in the project.	Customers and end users are among the most important stakeholder. Their needs vary according to how the project affects them. They must purchase the products, or the project will be a failure. Market research is needed to make the decision about further project proceedings. In addition, we must consider the ways in which the end users' lives change, and the features and innovations that could add benefit for them (at an acceptable cost).	External	WP1 T1.2, T1.3 WP5 T5.5 WP7 T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4, T7.7 WP8 T8.1, T8.5 WP9
Individuals and stakeholders in competition with OXIPRO or who have an interest in the project.	Government, regulatory bodies that permits and/or approves: Participation in consultation sessions to identify and bring requests for changes back to OXIPRO. The public probably will not be an important stakeholder audience for OXIPRO except where the public is inconvenienced by OXIPROs outcomes.	External	WP1 Task1.2, T1.3 WP5 T5.5 WP7 T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4, T7.7 WP8 T8.1, T8.5 WP9

Identification and allocation into internal and external stakeholders will be done considering the OXIPROs four stakeholder sectors. To categorise them we formulated questions helping to classify them into priority groups:

1. Who is affected positively or negatively by the project?
2. Who has the power to make it succeed (or fail)?
3. Who are the end users?
4. Who are potential investors/buyers?
5. Who has influence over other stakeholders?
6. Who could solve (cause) potential problems with the project?
7. Who has specialist skills which are crucial to the project?

Based on these questions, stakeholders are then arranged in a matrix that serves to categorise stakeholders according to two major characteristics:

- a) Willingness to participate in OXIPRO activities and interest in OXIPRO results or actions. (How willing is the stakeholder to engage? How likely is it that the stakeholder will be interested in participating in OXIPRO activities or use OXIPRO products?)
- b) Potential influence of the stakeholder towards OXIPRO project and its results. Here, one needs to ask how much influence the stakeholder has on concrete project tasks, actions, results.

This will be done for all stakeholder sectors.

Results of this are entered into a matrix developed by Mendelow [1] showing the potential influence/interest/impact of the stakeholder towards OXIPRO and its results. The Mendelow Stakeholder matrix (also known as the Stakeholder Analysis matrix and the Power-Interest matrix) is a simple framework to help manage stakeholders. Here, one needs to ask how much influence the stakeholder has on concrete project tasks, actions, results. Along the x- and y-axis, four fields are generated (Fig.3):

- Low influence/low interest
- Low influence/high interest
- High influence/low interest
- High influence/high interest

Fig 3.: Categories of stakeholders subdivided in groups according to their general needs

Based on the stakeholder's position in the matrix, they become divided into groups according to their priority (Figure 4) and the actions which should be taken towards the specific stakeholder (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Resulting priority groups

Figure 5: Resulting communication requirements

3.2.1 Geographic distribution of stakeholders

The OXIPRO consortium will ensure that by the end of the project the stakeholders registered include at least but will not be limited to representatives of all partner countries involved. The STAKEHOLDER REGISTER will enable stakeholders to be sorted according to country. The OXIPROs STAKEHOLDER REGISTER currently consist of data from 12 EU countries (BE, GR, DK, NL, IT, UK, FR, DE, FI, ES, SE, SI) plus three non-EU and/or EEA countries (NO, UK, TR). The geographic distribution of stakeholders is not restricted to OXIPRO partner countries.

3.3 Phase 3: Stakeholder map for communication strategy

Based on the stakeholder's position in the matrix the communication and reporting actions will be defined for targeted stakeholder communication and reporting measures, as shown in Table 3.2. This task will be done in accordance with and using measures from OXIPROs CDP (D7.4.)

Table 3.2 Communication and action plan depending on the stakeholder's priority

<p>Key players / Top priority:</p> <p>Those stakeholders that have a strong influence on OXIPRO are the most important and therefore will be prioritised for initial and regular contact. In addition, most of the active engagement activities will be designed to engage and collaborate with them. They will be regularly contacted, consulted, and informed about OXIPRO results and activities. Active engagement with OXIPRO will be achieved via social media posts (e.g., by tagging, inviting comments, following, etc.), press releases, the issuing of direct invitations to participate in project activities with the objective of sustaining their interest and active involvement.</p>
<p>Influencers / Handle with care:</p> <p>Little interest so far, but have high influence towards OXIPRO, fall under 'Meet their needs' category. The objective is to move such stakeholders to 'high influence/high interest' part of the matrix, thereof securing more and more actively engaged stakeholders who can exercise their influence to benefit the project. It means that the project consortium has the task to better inform these stakeholders and increase their curiosity about the project and its benefits to them.</p>
<p>Interested players / Need help to participate:</p> <p>It is highly unlikely for the project to increase the level of influence that stakeholders have in relation to OXIPRO. Therefore, interested stakeholders in this category shall be addressed to a lower extent. However, they will be kept informed and consulted. Their knowledge stemming from the OXIPRO project might also allow them to move to another matrix's quarter.</p>
<p>Passive players / low priority:</p> <p>Finally, the least effort will be taken to address passive identified stakeholders (low influence and low interest). Informing and trying to engage them would take a lot of effort, while their low influence would not pay off these efforts. Therefore, whenever partners decide that potential stakeholder is the passive one, such stakeholders are not considered further and not included to the Stakeholder list. However, they might still be addressed through generic communication channels (e.g., project website, social media, etc.), thus some of them might move towards becoming an interested stakeholder.</p>

After categorization into priority groups, we further differ between four areas: Industry, Society, Policy and Research. At the end, for each of the four target products we will have 13 different subgroups per

target product as shown in Table 3.3 = STAKEHOLDER MAP. In the priority group of passive stakeholders, we will not further differentiate the areas.

Table 3.3 STAKEHOLDER MAP

A	Liquid detergent			B	Sun Care			C	Clinical Nutraceuticals			D	Home textiles					
key player	industry		1	key player	industry		1	key player	industry		1	key player	industry		1			
	research		2		research		2		research		2		research		2	research		2
	society		3		society		3		society		3		society		3	society		3
	policy		4		policy		4		policy		4		policy		4	policy		4
Influencer	industry		5	Influencer	industry		5	Influencer	industry		5	Influencer	industry		5			
	research		6		research		6		research		6		research		6	research		6
	society		7		society		7		society		7		society		7	society		7
	policy		8		policy		8		policy		8		policy		8	policy		8
Interested	industry		9	Interested	industry		9	Interested	industry		9	Interested	industry		9			
	research		10		research		10		research		10		research		10	research		10
	society		11		society		11		society		11		society		11	society		11
	policy		12		policy		12		policy		12		policy		12	policy		12
Passive	industry		13	Passive	industry		13	Passive	industry		13	Passive	industry		13			
	research																	
	society																	
	policy																	

This table will be used to generate specific activities and mailing list according to the needs of the stakeholders. The principle behind is as following:

Assuming target stakeholders should be from Industry and key player and influencers. Individuals listed in A1 and A5 will be candidates as well as from B1/B5, C1/C5 and D1/D5 (Figure 6).

Following this principle, it becomes easy to sort the stakeholders depending on the requirement of OXIPROs activities.

A	Liquid detergent			B	Sun Care			C	Clinical NutraCeuticals			D	Home textil					
key player	industry		1	key player	industry		1	key player	industry		1	key player	industry		1			
	research		2		research		2		research		2		research		2	research		2
	society		3		society		3		society		3		society		3	society		3
	policy		4		policy		4		policy		4		policy		4	policy		4
Influencer	industry		5	Influencer	industry		5	Influencer	industry		5	Influencer	industry		5			
	research		6		research		6		research		6		research		6	research		6
	society		7		society		7		society		7		society		7	society		7
	policy		8		policy		8		policy		8		policy		8	policy		8
Interested	industry		9	Interested	industry		9	Interested	industry		9	Interested	industry		9			
	research		10		research		10		research		10		research		10	research		10
	society		11		society		11		society		11		society		11	society		11
	policy		12		policy		12		policy		12		policy		12	policy		12
Passive	industry		13	Passive	industry		13	Passive	industry		13	Passive	industry		13			
	research																	
	society																	
	policy																	

Figure 6: Example of the possible selection of stakeholders: Behind each Number a list of individuals fitting in this category are listed and will be extracted and merged for the action targeted

3.4. Phase 4: Stakeholder engagement

OXIPRO's multi stakeholder engagement strategy entails the following activities: anticipation, reflection, engagement, and action (AREA) to influence the direction and trajectory of OXIPRO's research and innovation (Table 3.4).

Table 3.4 OXIPRO's AREA strategy to engage with stakeholders

AREA	User-centred dimension	Multi-actor dimension	Intraconsortium dimension
Anticipate	Consumer interviews (WP1), Habit surveys (WP7), Survey of ethical, legal, and societal concerns (WP1), Risk analysis (WP6)	Landscape analysis (WP1), Overall sustainability (WP6), Risk assessment (WP6), Market analysis and feasibility studies (WP1)	Lecture series (WP1), Scale-up modelling (WP4); Co-creation workshops (WP1)
Reflect	Awareness-raising campaigns (WP7), Meet-a-Scientist (WP1), Design-thinking, Persona Modelling, Consumer journey mapping (WP1).	Life cycle thinking; Circular Economy (WP6); Policy briefs and reports (WP1)	Open Science & FAIR data; Life cycle thinking
Engage	Surveys, open co-creative events (WP1, WP7), consumer panellists' (WP5)	Policy meetings, Policy workshops, Open policy events (WP1), round table talks, world cafes (WP1),	Innovation Boot Camp, Co-creative workshops (WP1), Consortium meetings (WP8)
Act	Contingency plan, Consortium meetings, Management committee, Scientific committee, Manager roles, Advisory Board (WP8), Technology adjustments (WP2-WP5), Consortium agreement (WP8), Data management plan (WP8), SOPs (WP1), ISO standards (WP1, WP6), Open science policy (WP8)		

Measures that OXIPRO will take towards engaging stakeholders according to the four types of stakeholder's priorities are summarised in Table 3.5 and shown as an example in Fig. 7.

Table 3.5: Key actions to engage with the different stakeholders' categories.

	Influence/Interest	Key actions towards such stakeholder
Key stakeholders	high influence and high interest	Objective: To collaborate and manage this group Directly engaged at the earliest possibility Continuous communication built by sending project updates, consulting their opinions, inviting to events, etc.
Influencers	high influence but low interest	Objective: To keep this group's needs satisfied. Efforts taken to make them Key stakeholders. Communication actions stressing OXIPRO's benefits and raising curiosity.
Interested stakeholders	low influence but high interest	Objective: To keep this group informed. Continuous communication to inform about project progress, actions, and results. Potential consultation regarding areas of stakeholders' interest (especially regarding specific questions or uncertainties that the project faces)
Passive stakeholders	low influence and low interest	Objective: To monitor this group with minimum effort. No specific actions taken to address this group. Might get informed through general communication actions of the project (e.g., website)

Figure 7: Communication strategy and action plan for stakeholder engagement based on the stakeholder map

At the stage of the submission of D1.1 the following activities are already implemented, initiated, or planned. However, as stakeholder mapping is a continuous process and strongly depending on interaction within the partners and the external stakeholders’ adjustments might be needed.

In the following some of OXIPROs planned stakeholder measures are described. The boxes represent the different categories of stakeholders according to Table 3.2. Crosses indicates whether involvement of the relevant stakeholder group is planned its priority or involvement is represented by crosses in descending order from large to small.

Interviews, Surveys and Questionnaires (month 6-48)	x	x	x	x
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Semi-structured interviews with consumers and consumer organizations to elicit views on key challenges (e.g., GMO issues) relating to OXIPRO will be executed. In addition, a survey based on literature and databases will identify national regulations that promote or hamper the application of the new enzymes and show potential opportunities or risks for introducing the technologies developed in OXIPRO. At least 20 interviews with representatives from the participating partner countries policymakers will draw out views. The major outcome of this task is to draft a minimum of two policy briefs relating to the European Bioeconomy strategy and other relevant strategies, outlining rationales for policy alternatives or courses of action we recommend because of the findings.

Capacity building (month 6-48)

X	X	x	x
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Capacity building measures to set up a framework to facilitate transnational cooperation of OXIPROs relevant stakeholders. This will be addressed by providing access to OXIPRO information, repositories, and recourses such as e.g., databases and homepage(s) open access publications, training activities (e.g., lecture series, T1.2.) either intra-consortial to strength the OXIPRO framework, or extra-consortial (customised e.g., for FNR-Sister projects to coordinate and foster alliances) and to the public. Special focus will be given to key players and influencers (inclusion e.g., via bi-directional consultation and expert advice or coaching).

Round table talks (Year 1/3)

X	X		
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The multi-actor stakeholder group (gathering research, industry, and policy stakeholders) will be engaged by active inclusion in form of at least two round table talks and at least two world cafés during the 1st and the 3rd year. Stakeholders will help understanding the challenges of the practical and technical implementation at institutional-, administrative and monetary level and which needs to be overcome to enable OXIPRO's innovation transfer. One round table talk will be organized with the multi-actor stakeholders and providing links with project officer and policy officers. Another round table talk will be organized as a joint policy meeting with sister FNR-16 projects and policy makers to agree on a harmonized form to deliver results for efficient feedback into policymaking. Findings of the round table talks will be used to develop question to be addressed in the world cafés and enter research agenda roadmaps, feasibility studies and market replication analyses (T.1.3).

World Café (Year 1/3)

X	X	x	
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The world-cafe, open a place for the participants to get to know each other's different perspectives, to discover different approaches to a topic, to learn new forms of interaction, to listen carefully, to question, to discuss. Within the world cafés multiple stakeholders will get together to discuss identified inefficiencies and to develop co-creative solutions towards the delivery of targeted innovation-led solutions. A world cafe takes about 45 minutes to three hours. The participants sit together in small groups round a table. "Moderators" address appropriate questions and bring people into a constructive dialogue ensuring the linking of the findings from the different discussion sessions. In the course two or three different questions are discussed in successive discussion sessions of 15 to 30 minutes at all tables. (Participants will rotate, moderator stay). The World Café closes with a reflection phase. One world café will take place with representatives of business/industry and consumer associations. Another world café will be open for a broader spectrum of participants, targeting the

potential end-users. Outcomes of the world cafes will identify core questions to be processed in co-creation workshops with members of the consortium.

Co-Creation (Year 1/3)

X	X	X	
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In one 1st year co-creative workshop, the consortium will come together for the joint creative processing of research questions relating to OXIPROs enzyme targets, product applications and value chains. Outcomes of this, including four specification sheets on enzyme, process, and product requirements for each of the innovation cases, will be gathered for work in WP2-WP6 and continuously updated.

Consortium meetings (annually)

X	x		
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Key stakeholders (and influences) might be invited to consortium meeting to consult them, learn from their perspectives/opinions and to keep them on track and curious.

Direct mailing (Month 6-48)

X	X		
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To avoid bombarding stakeholder identified as key player or influencer with information which might not be of interest for them, they will receive tailor made information to keep or bring them on board. This will also improve interaction and engagement with them.

Videos (Year1)

X	X	X	X
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Explanatory videos will be produced at the beginning and during the runtime of OXIPRO describing the project, its objectives and expected impacts aimed at explaining the project focus using non-technical terminology. They will be hosted on YouTube and visible on the project website and distributed through the different dissemination channels (T.7.2).

Social networks (month 3-48)

x	x	X	X
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Social networks will be used to actively involve an online community represented by the target audiences identified with a twofold objective: to inform them about OXIPRO and encourage them to actively contribute to dialogue on the project issues and topics, also enhancing public understanding. A social media strategy will be developed at the beginning of the project to select the most suitable channels to be activated for the project (e.g., Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, or YouTube). In addition, existing discussion groups and communities will be used, through which the project will actively post news and topics for discussion through its own account (T.7.1)

Newsletter (twice per year)

x	x	X	X
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A periodic project eNewsletter will be issued every six months to provide information on the project activities and developments. Each issue will be distributed depending on the stakeholder's priority via OXIPROs dissemination channels.

Delphi survey (Year3)

		X	X
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Identification of potential educational, cultural, gender- or generation derived issues will be actioned through a Delphi survey to transform opinion into group consensus regarding the end users view of production (e.g., biotechnology for tailor-made applications), consumption habits, adoption or rejection or use of the results/products. Outcomes will be considered for internal use (responsiveness) and will also be used to generate a catalogue of recommendations to address aspects in future exploitation measures (T.1.3). Information will also feed into social impact assessment (WP6).

Direct personal exchange "Meet a Scientist" (Year 3)

x	x	X	X
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In the 3rd year, OXIPRO will run two "Meet a Scientist" events in the European Biotech Week to build relationships between academic scientists and community members to foster dialogue and trust.

3.5 Stakeholder mapping: practical implementation

In this section we present the practicalities that lead to the creation of OXIPRO's initial stakeholder register including activities and contribution by the consortium partners how the Stakeholder register was created. The stakeholder register differs from Stakeholder map or Stakeholder Engagement plans as it is focused only on each stakeholder's name and contact details rather than their power and interest or their engagement strategy.

In addition, we present the policies we follow regarding stakeholder's data.

Collection of data: The collection of data will be supported by all partners. For the collection of data, each partner received a template (Annex 1) to be filled in and submitted to SBSM/NORCE. Identification of stakeholder groups will leverage the potential that the OXIPRO partners can provide via their already existing contacts. Stakeholders' areas relevant for OXIPRO are from the research, industry, decision makers and the society (consumer sectors). We aim to engage a minimum of 2 representatives per KSA from each stakeholder sector of each participating country and, if possible, beyond. The templates will be analysed corresponding to the method described above and individuals/stakeholder will be sorted into groups following the structure shown in Table 3.3. In

addition, data from the areas/sectors/groups mentioned above which are public available or accessible will enter the stakeholder register while always respecting the GDPR.

NORCE/SBSM thus can generate pseudonymised mailing list used for stakeholder engagement.

3.5.1 Data protection

D1.1 is also closely linked to D9.1 and D9.4 (WP Ethics) because it gathers personal data (names, contact details of the stakeholders) and thus need to follow data management requirements of GDPR. The stakeholder mapping OXIPRO therefore requires meeting the rules agreed in WP9, with its deliverables concerning ethical requirements needed while the collection, storing and processing of personal information. Therefore, for the collection of data will be done in a secured environment within SBSMs own highly secure cloud and underlies joint data control with NORCE. Access to data will be restricted to those consortium partners who are dependent on the information (WP Task) and who have signed the data transfer agreement (DTA) for outgoing data. For the collection of data SBSM/NORCE will share a DTA for incoming data to be signed by both parties before data collection. Mailing list resulting from the analysis will be managed by SBSM/NORCE to ensure that individuals who are in the lists will not be identifiable by third parties.

The individual tasks and procedures to collect data are detailed described in the ethics deliverable D9.1.(Confidential) A short summary is given herein:

Research: To identify representatives we will contact the coordinators from previously and future funded projects under Horizon 2020 / Horizon Europe and national networks or projects that are related to the OXIPRO research programme. Via these contacts we will recruit representatives specific for interests in the OXIPRO activities.

Industry: For recruiting representatives from companies, we will explore existing research projects and networks and if companies from these networks are relevant for the OXIPRO research. Additional routes will through networks on the European level (e.g., European Bioeconomy Network, www.eubionet.eu), the national level (e.g., Enterprise Europe Network EEN) or regional industry clusters and innovation networks (e.g., CLIB Cluster for Industrial Biotechnology in Germany, Biotech North in Norway).

Policy: We will contact national Ministries for relevant representatives as participants for our research activities. Additionally, we will identify larger-scale NGOs to include their interests in OXIPRO's research.

Society: Here, we will first establish contact with existing European Federations and Associations to recruiting participants from the European perspective. With the help of these federations, we will identify reliable consumer associations in countries covering a min. of three of the countries of OXIPRO.

4 List of stakeholders' needs for each stakeholder group.

This report allows for better understanding of the different types of stakeholders and exploration of the main benefits OXIPRO can offer them. This information will be further elaborated in OXIPRO's dissemination strategy, social awareness strategy and stakeholder engagement and thus influence work of other WPs within OXIPRO as described in Table 2.1.

In the following examples are listed to which OXIPRO can contribute:

Researchers needs

- ✓ understanding of how certain technological solutions can be used to address current challenges
- ✓ learning and understanding fast emerging new trends and technologies,
- ✓ learning and understanding to deal with external threats such as further restrictions caused by pandemic scenarios
- ✓ understand the opportunities of knowledge transfer and applicability of the research results,
- ✓ strengthen (international) cooperation with industry,
- ✓ strengthen (international) cooperation with academia,
- ✓ connect with influential and innovative SMEs,
- ✓ access to innovation, skills, and new technologies,
- ✓ understanding perspectives, needs, and requirements of policy makers,
- ✓ understanding perspectives, needs, and requirements of industry,
- ✓ understanding perspectives, needs, and requirements of the society,
- ✓ networking and collaboration opportunities with industry, regulatory bodies, and policy makers

Industrial needs

- ✓ understanding of the new and innovative effective & high-quality to improve their products, services, and business models,
- ✓ possibility to find partners that may provide innovative results and outputs that positively affect their processes or products (e.g., environment friendly production),
- ✓ strengthen cooperation with academia and connect with researchers,
- ✓ understanding the practical applicability of OXIPRO's results,
- ✓ making potential investors aware of OXIPRO's potential,
- ✓ supporting the innovation (and business development) of inventors.

Policy needs

- ✓ understanding how their funding has been invested,

- ✓ understanding and adoption of the new and innovative technologies and products, and their potential,
- ✓ understanding the researchers' perspectives, needs and requirements,
- ✓ understanding the existing barriers in R&I in sectorial policies
- ✓ understanding the existing barriers in R&I by different national rules
- ✓ understanding the existing barriers in R&I

Societal needs:

- ✓ understanding how they tax money has been invested,
- ✓ understanding how certain technological solutions can be used to address grand challenges
- ✓ learning and understanding latest trends, technologies, and products which might have a positive or negative impact on them,
- ✓ losing fear of contact with new and emerging technologies,
- ✓ become interested in new products (e.g., environment-friendly).

5 References

[1] Mendelow, A. L. (1991) 'Environmental Scanning: The Impact of the Stakeholder Concept'. Proceedings From the Second International Conference on Information Systems 407-418. Cambridge, MA.

6 Annex 1 (data collection template)

PARTNER NO		Short Name										
Stakeholder Name	Belongs to	Stakeholder relationship	Role / Profession	Affiliation (if applicable)	Website (if applicable)	Address	Phone number	Cell phone	E-Mail	Your Name (contact provider)	Can we refer to you when contacting this person?	
	other	internal	Reseacher								<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	
	Liquid detergent	external	CEO								<input type="checkbox"/> No	
	Sun care	relative/family	Owner									
	Textiles	colleague	Regulatory body									
	NutraCeuticals	neighborhood	Staffmember									
		friend	Board member									
			Politician									
			Lobbyist									
			Manager									
			Technician									
			Gen Milenium									
			Gen X									
			Gen Y									
			Gen Z									
			Manufacturer									
			Customer									
			User									
			other									
			NN									

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